

A New Approach to Connect Workmen to the Needy – SEVAK

Farooq Sunar Mahammad¹, Sutraye Nikhitha²

^{1,2}Department of CSE, Santhiram Engineering College, Nandyal. Andhra Pradesh, India-518501

Email id: farooq.cse@srecnandyal.edu.in¹, 19x51a05c3@srecnandyal.edu.in²

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Abstract

In Our daily life, we have been come across different works, among them we can manage only a few works, but not all works can be done by our own, some works will need technicians, some works will need Workmen and others. If there are workmen available near us will be fine. But what if there are no workmen available near us, or what if we went to a new location and needed a workman or a technician for some works. Now-a-days, there are so many people who are unemployed. They are suffering from lack of food , shelter , and common needs. Here is the best solution for all these problems. We are making a bridge for connecting the workmen to the needy. This is an Android Application, where any Workmen can register himself by submitting his details. The users can access the Workmen data by selecting the appropriate category and Location. Then the user can call directly to the workmen from the app. This application is useful for the survival of unemployed people in different areas , locations, or states etc.,.

Keywords: *Workmen, Service, Location, Unemployed, Survival.*

I. Introduction

Not all works can be done by our own some works needed labor, some works needed repair man, some works needed experts we don't know all kind of workmen for all of our works. We need to go out and should search for the labor or workers for our works. If the proper worker available for that will be fine. what in the case of no workmen available for our work or unable to go out for searching them? Then that will hurt us for finishing our works. Suppose if we went to a new location, there we met a trouble with our vehicle, then we should rush to a nearest repair shop or service center, but we don't know where the service center or work station is available. By seeing Fig.1 , so in this case we can get the details of the workers/Repair man/Labor/ Technicians / others details and contact no as per location. So, we can have workers to the needy, if any problem is arise for us, there will be no person to help us ,in order to avoid this problem, we can give job opportunity to the unemployed. So that , they can easily solve the problem for the needy people. This app is not only useful for one category workers, but also for the many number of category workers, who are unemployed. Rather than one person, community of workers, category list of workers can help this opportunity. By installing this app, we won't need someone's help, and there is no need of asking information. Simply, we can open the app, we will find the workers nearby us and we can explain them our problem. When this app is implemented, then we can save out time, energy and we can take look after the other works.

II. Motivation

Most of the works will need a technician or a workman to complete them, only a few works can be done by us in home/Office/Factory like Cooking, Cleaning, and some other minor works. In case of some occasions we may need a cook, or a cleaner, or an Event organizer. We can search those workmen in the app as per the location.. we can contact them with the details available in the app. For example, if we develop an application for carpentry work, then only the carpenter community will develop. Likewise, if we develop any application, that application is not only useful for one community, but also useful for the other category workers (or) community workers like Television Mechanics, Electricians, Plumbers, etc. By that, we are developing different types of community workers. So, if we succeed in this development, some lakhs of unemployed are getting jobs, so that they can survive their families. For example, we want a Maid. We don't know who are maid and who are needy to do work in Home/Office. By developing this application, we can provide the jobs. Who doesn't have proper basic needs like food, shelter, etc., we can provide them jobs. Because of this, the job opportunities are increased and the majority of unemployed will be changed to employed. By this application, we are motivating the unemployed people. This app is free of cost, unemployed and poor people can utilize the opportunity for their bright future.

III. Objective

The Main Objective of this paper is to connect a common man with the different categories of workmen /Technicians/Labor for their daily life requirements. The Main Moto of this app is to develop a vast number of unemployed to employed workers. Generally in our native locations we can manage to get the workmen or labor early, but in the case of a new location/area it is hard to find a worker or technician. From the worker point of view the app act as a earning platform. In a common criterion whenever we need a technician or a driver or any workers, we would contact an office of broker who arrange these technicians. These technicians are working under them for a monthly pay. So even though the labor is working they won't get the pay for their work every time, because they are working for a monthly pay. For example, we are living in an area. We all know about the people, workers, routes nearby us. Suddenly, if we move to the different place (or) different area (or) different state, we don't know about the people, workers, and routes. If any problem is raised, for example we got TV repair, we don't where the mechanics are and we have to ask neighbors (or) we have to go out and search for the mechanic. By this, we can loss our energy, time and there will be risk. Then how can we overcome our problem. For that situation (or) problem, we are developing SEVAK app. By installing this app, you can know the workers nearby you and can save our time, energy and we can go to our work [2]. So that, the problem can solved easily. But in this application, there are no middle man between a worker and the client, directly a workman will register with his details, then the client who need them will contact directly. This is the simple process of getting workers as per location very easily.

IV. Related Work.

Currently there are few applications working in providing the contact information of a business. Those are working on B2B (Business to Business) Policy, where the user is provided with the

business, shops and manufacturers information. Where there is 50-50 probability of service availability and client satisfaction [1]. The B2B system needs a workspace and an registered address for listing the business details in the application. Apart from that the B2B system have the workmen, where they are working monthly basis, so they are not profitable for the work done by them as per the client requirement for service at their doorstep [3]. The existing system has some drawbacks, some of them are Not every business will have the workmen to give service, most of the businesses are product based but not service based and No workmen is directly benefited by the existed business listing applications, The existed business applications are needed a specific address and a work infrastructure to get registered. There is simple example, now-a-days, lots of home delivery apps are implemented. These apps are belong to only one community, that means we take Zomato, swiggi. These apps are related to food. In this app, they can order the food and it can deliver within minutes. This app is only for delivering the food. Likewise, we are implementing an application, which can help to solve our basic needs problems like TV repairs, Car Trouble, Plumbing, Electric Repairs and so on. This app is helpful for those unemployed and can save the time, work for the clients. Solving our basic need problems is only SEVAK.

V. Proposed Method

Here is the new system irrespective of a business address and a work infrastructure. The proposed system is not based on Business to Business and Business to client[4]. This system is completely based on Service to Client. Here the workmen/technician will get registered with his/her details like Name, Age, Experience, Location, Mobile number and his work Category. The workmen who registered with his details will have a login credentials like Email and password. By using these login credentials, the workmen will get access to his/her profile and can edit the details. The User who is accessing the data would not require any login or registration process, just by downloading the application, the user can select the category and location/city. By selecting the two filters the workmen available in that location will be appeared along with the details like Name, Categories of work, location and mobile number, then the user is able to call him directly. Then after getting the service the user will pay directly to the workmen who did the service. This is the Service to customer platform [5]. We can access this at anywhere, and also by developing this application, we can provide great future for the needy people not only surrounded by our locality, area but also throughout the world. This application is helpful for the workers who are TV mechanics, Plumbers, Electricians, Carpenters, Car repair mechanics and for different kinds of daily minute problems. This application can give opportunity to the unemployed and poor people. This application is not only useful for Technicians, but also for labors.

VI. Implementation

Implementation is done on Android Studio—. Android Development Tools (ADT) is a plugin for the Android Studio that is designed to give a powerful, integrated environment in which to build Android applications. ADT extends the capabilities of Android Studio to let you quickly set up new Android projects, create an application UI, add packages based on the Android Framework API, debug applications using the Android SDK tools, and even export signed (or unsigned) .apk files in order to distribute your application.

Fig.1, Search Workmen by user

we have implemented this using Android Studio with a fine interface, keeping in mind that it can be useful to all the users irrespective of the age, gender and education. As we see most of the application available are difficult to use for illiterate peoples. But our application is very simple and easy to use.

VII. Results and Discussions

Fig.2. Home page of the SEVAK

Fig. 3 Search for Workmen

Fig.4. List of workmen

Fig. 5. Workmen details with call option

The User and workmen has to register first into this application. Workmen can register by providing the details like experience, type of work, contact number, name and address, the details has to be approved by the admin before it has to be listed. Where as user has to register just by providing the basic details. By using Fig.3, After login the user can search for workmen.

After Registering, we need to login, then we can search for a workmen by selecting the category and location. In Fig.4, A List will be displayed with all available workmen with their contact numbers.

In Fig.5, A list will appear, we have a option of calling directly from the app, we can call the workmen directly and contact him.

VIII. Conclusion and Future Enhancement

This Mobile Application will help most of the workmen or skilled people who are not having a proper income source and a work infrastructure to work and those who are ready to work at our doorstep, The Application will become a best connective platform for all the users in the most of the towns and cities who need a workmen or technicians for their home need or office uses. The app doesn't require any office or registered workplace to become a registered workman.

The application initially available only in the top 50 cities/Towns of Andhra Pradesh statue, the next upgrade of this application will be available all over the India, which access the workmen and user's GPS location and work with that location. The app will be available all over the country which is irrespective of a location and state. The up gradation will have the workmen rating option which helps to choose the best and perfect workmen for the user needs.

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